

Electrochemical Studies on Rubber Based Cation Exchange Membranes

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Rubber based ion exchange membranes from indigenously obtained CNSL resin have been studied. Membrane potentials have been measured with change in binder content and external solution concentration. Membrane with 16% rubber is found to have nearly ideal permselectivity in dilute solutions.

The characteristic electrochemical properties of ion exchange membranes have been the subject of investigation of several workers¹. Membranes of desired cation or anion selectivity can be prepared by modifying the process of polymerisation. Homogeneous membranes can be cast during the preparation². To increase the mechanical properties of these membranes, the ion exchange material is mixed in proper proportion with an inert binder³ like polyethylene etc., such membranes being easy to handle in large scale operations. In this investigation, membranes prepared from CNSL resin⁴ using crepe rubber as binder in different proportions are used. Rubber was found to be a compatible binder for this ion exchange material⁵. Membrane potentials have been studied and the dependence of transport number on binder content and external electrolyte concentration has been reported in this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL

Membranes: The preparation of the rubber based membranes, their capacities and sorption properties have already been reported⁶. A small circular sample of the membrane was converted to hydrogen form by about 20 hrs' contact with 5% HCl. After thorough leaching of the membrane, it was converted to sodium form by 4-N NaCl. This was done repeatedly till no more acid was liberated. The membrane was washed with distilled water. The membrane was then equilibrated with a sodium chloride solution of concentration equal to the average of the two NaCl concentrations used in the cell. Membranes with binder content less than 16% were not investigated as these did not possess adequate strength.

1. J. T. Clarke., "Ion transport across membranes", Acad. Press, N. Y., 1954; K. Sollner, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1950, **97**, 1390.
2. W. Juda, N. W. Rosenberg, J. A. Marinsky and A. N. Kasper, *J. A. C.S.*, 1952, **74**, 3736.
W. E. Graydon and R. J. Stewart, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1955, **59**, 87.
C. W. Davies and G. D. Yoeman, *Trans. Farad. Soc.*, 1953, **49**, 968.
3. D. K. Hale and McCaulay, *Trans. Farad. Soc.*, 1961, **57**, 134.
4. N. Krishnaswamy, K. P. Govindan and R. N. Pandya, *Chem. Ind. (London)*, 1957, 1456.
5. N. Krishnaswamy and N. P. Suryanarayana, *J. Polymer. Sci.*, 1963, **81**, 491.
6. N. P. Suryanarayana and K. M. Joshi, *J. Appld. Polymer. Sci.*, 1964, **8**, 1491; 1965, **9**, 941.

Cell: A two compartment cell with flanges was employed. Each compartment had an inlet for solution and for a standard reference electrode. The conditioned membrane was held between the flanges of the two compartments which were tightened with clamping rings provided with screws. The arrangement was leak proof.

Electrodes: Reference electrodes used were Ag/AgCl electrodes prepared according to standard methods. The potential of the reference electrode was checked before and after each experiment. The cell used was:

The cell was thermostatted at $30^\circ \pm 0.1$. Potentials were measured on a Pye potentiometer using 0.1 multiplier reading accurately to 0.1 mv. The steady state value of the potential was recorded that was about 15-20 minutes after setting the cell. The steady state value was found to be constant even after 24 hrs.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data obtained from e.m.f. measurement of the cell at different external solution concentrations with membranes having binder content 16, 20, 25.5 and 33.3 percent are given in table I.

TABLE I

Sodium chloride concentration $C_2 = 2 C_1$

E_o : e.m.f. of the cell with ideally cation permselective membrane

C_1	E_o	$-E_{\text{obs}}$ (membrane 1)	$-E_{\text{obs}}$ (membrane 2)	$-E_{\text{obs}}$ (membrane 3)	$-E_{\text{obs}}$ membrane 4)
0.0625	32.5mv	32.3mv	25.0 mv.	26.1 mv	25.2 mv
0.125	32.5	32.2	25.1	25.3	23.9
0.25	32.46	31.4	25.0	23.8	24.0
0.5	33.6	30.2	22.9	22.9	23.8
1.0	36.38	28.9	22.2	22.1	23.3
2.0	40.1	27.1	20.9	22.1	22.1
Membrane 1	: Rubber content: 16%; capacity	2.0 meq./gm;	moisture: 50%		
Membrane 2	,, 20%; ,,	1.67 ,,	,, 48%		
Membrane 3	,, 25%; ,,	0.25 ,,	,, 45%		
Membrane 4	,, 33.3%; ,,	0.15 ,,	,, 43%		

The e.m.f. of the cell under investigation is made of electrode/solution potentials, phase boundary potentials and the diffusion potential inside the membrane. These can be evaluated and on adding the individual contributions, the total cell potential is⁷

$$E = \frac{2 RT}{F} \ln \frac{a_{\pm}(1)}{a_{\pm}(2)} - \frac{2 RT}{F} \int_1^2 \bar{t}_y \, d \ln a_{\pm}$$

where a_{\pm} represents the mean activity and \bar{t}_y is the anion transport number inside the membrane. For an ideally permselective cation membrane ($\bar{t}_y=0$), the potential of the cell

is given by the first term in the above equation. (E_0 in table-I). The value of the cell potential is seen to increase with external solution concentration showing that t_y at higher concentrations is not zero and that co-ions are participating in the transport process. The permselectivity is also seen to depend on the binder content so that even at very low concentrations, changing the binder content from 16% to 20% affects the property of the membrane remarkably.

Making an assumption that \bar{t}_y is linear in $\ln a_{\pm}$ for small variations in concentrations on two sides of the membrane (this assumption is shown not to affect the result seriously), the cationic transport number is then $\bar{t}_+ = E/E_0$. The variation of the average cation transport number is plotted against average concentration in Fig. 1. From this plot, it is seen that the 16% binder content membrane compares favourably with Nepton CR 51 (reported in ref. 2a). However it is curious to note that the \bar{t}_y/C plots for 20 to 33.5 percent binder do not show a regular variation amongst themselves though their capacity varies from 1.6 to 0.15.

Expressing the quantity \bar{t}_+ as $\bar{C}_+ \bar{D}_+ / (\bar{C}_+ \bar{D}_+ + \bar{C}_- \bar{D}_-)$ where \bar{D} 's are the diffusion coefficients of the ions and \bar{C} 's are the ionic concentrations in the membrane, the ratio \bar{D}_- / \bar{D}_+ can be evaluated. \bar{C}_- is obtained from sorption data, \bar{C}_+ is the sum of fixed charge per liter of the membrane and the sorbed Na_+ concentration per liter which in turn is equal to \bar{C}_- (assuming no ion pair formation). Table II gives these calculations.

TABLE II

Average conc	Membrane 1				Average Conc.	Membrane 2			
	\bar{t}_+	\bar{C}_-	\bar{C}_+	\bar{D}_-/\bar{D}_+		\bar{t}_+	\bar{C}_-	\bar{C}_+	\bar{D}_-/\bar{D}_+
0.188	0.99	0.09	1.04	—	0.188	0.80	0.16	0.29	0.806
0.375	0.97	0.14	1.09	0.24	0.375	0.76	0.26	0.39	0.89
0.75	0.89	0.27	1.22	0.57	0.75	0.68	0.47	0.60	1.04
1.5	0.81	0.52	1.47	0.66	1.5	0.62	0.74	0.87	1.03
3.0	0.67	1.05	2.00	1.89	3.0	0.51	1.87	1.99	1.82

Figure 1. 1 : 16%; 2: 20%; 3: 25%; 4: 33.3% rubber membrane.

The mobility ratio \bar{D}/\bar{D}_+ in the two membranes is seen to increase with external solution concentration. Between the two membranes, the one with lower binder content shows lower values of mobility ratio at identical concentration. The deviation from ideal permselectivity of the membrane is thus related to the mobility ratio. This is according to observed behaviour as at low concentrations, exclusion of the co-ion takes place and the diffusion contribution of the co-ion is negligible while at higher concentrations, the co-ions participate in the diffusion process. The mobility ratios even at low concentrations in these membranes are somewhat high the reason being that the electrolyte is present in small quantity in the space between the resin granule and the binder thus offering a path through which co-ion diffusion can take place.

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